

Crystal and molecular structure of ethyl-(1,4-dibenzyloxy-2,3-naphthalene)-diacetate[†]

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In an attempted synthesis of radermachol (1), we had the occasion to prepare ethyl-(1,4-dibenzyloxy-2,3-naphthalene)-diacetate (2) for further structural modification. This paper describes the synthesis and the X-ray structure determination of compound 2.

A red pigment designated as radermachol was isolated from *Radermachera xylocarpa* K. Schum., and its structure (1) was assigned by a single crystal X-ray analysis¹. Radermachol possesses a unique fused ring system containing one five-, three six-, and one seven-membered rings. The rings A and E are planar while the seven-membered ring has a boat conformation and the rings B, C and D are slightly non-planar.

The total synthesis of radermachol has been reported in earlier publications^{2,3}. In preliminary studies for the synthesis of 1, we prepared 2 and attempted the conversion to 3 for further modifications.

Results and Discussion

For the attempted synthesis of 3, we prepared ethyl-(1,4-dibenzyloxy-2,3-naphthalene)-diacetate (2) by the sequence of reactions shown in Scheme 1. The Diels-Alder adduct (4) was prepared in 72% yield by reaction of 1,4-naphthoquinone with 1,3-butadiene in acetic acid⁴. The adduct 4 was treated with NaH in CD₃SOCD₃ and benzyl chloride to give the corresponding dibenzyloxy compound

(5). Treatment of 5 with OsO₄ gave the corresponding epoxide (6) which was cleaved with acid to give the *trans*-diol (7). Periodic acid oxidation of the diol (7) afforded the dialdehyde (8) which upon oxidation with Kiliani reagent gave the dicarboxylic acid (9). The carboxylic acid was esterified with ethanol and H₂SO₄ to give the ethylester (2).

Scheme 1

Compound 2 has bulky group on the four adjacent carbon atoms and appears to be symmetrical but is sterically hindered. In order to determine if compound 2 possesses symmetry, we carried out an X-ray crystal structure determination. In a previous investigation⁵, the X-ray crystal structure of the tetracyclic ring system of 6,7-benzo-3,4-(1,4-dimethoxy-2,3-naphtho)-1,5-dioxosuberane containing the rings A, B, C, and D of radermachol (1) showed a folding of two planar parts of the carbon skeleton about the axis passing through C8 and C16 of the seven-membered ring C.

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

X-Ray crystal structure of (2) :

The diffraction data for **2** were measured and analyzed by one of us (G.A.R.) during the 1999 ACA Summer Course in crystallography at the University of Georgia. Crystals of **2** used in the diffraction study had dimensions of 0.4×0.5×0.5 mm (Table 1). The Nonius Kappa CCD X-ray system with M_0 $K\alpha$ X-ray radiation was used to collect a total of 300 frames of a combination of ϕ and ω scans to fill the Ewald sphere. The data collection strategy was calculated using the Nonius Collect Suite of programs. Each frame was exposed for 20 s; a frame rotation of 1° was employed. A total of 21088 reflections with $2.91^\circ < \theta < 27.48^\circ$ were used in the refinement of the unit cell : $a = 8.7165(2)$ Å, $b = 26.0022(5)$ Å, $c = 12.6809(3)$ Å, $\beta = 105.3227(1)^\circ$, $V = 2773.2(1)$ Å³. The space group was determined to be the monoclinic $P2_1/n$ (#14) from systematic absences. The total number of unique reflection after the merging was 6515 representing a data completeness of 99.8%. The resolution range of the data was 7.00 to 0.77 Å.

Table 1. Crystal data and intensity measurements for **2**

Nature of the crystals	Colourless cubes
Molecular formula	$C_{32}H_{32}O_6$
Molecular weight	512.60
Crystal dimensions	0.40×0.50×0.50 mm
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Lattice type	Primitive
Lattice parameters	$a = 8.7165(2)$ Å $b = 26.0022(5)$ Å $c = 12.6809(3)$ Å $\beta = 105.3227(1)^\circ$
Unit cell volume	$2773.2(1)$ Å ³
Space group	$P2_1/n$ (#14)
Z	4
D_{calc}	1.228 g cm ⁻³
$F(000)$	1088.00
μ ($M_0K\alpha$)	0.84 cm ⁻¹
Diffractometer	Nonius KappaCCD
Radiation	$M_0K\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71069$ Å) graphite monochromated
No. of total reflections measured	6515
Corrections	Lorenz-polarization Secondary extinction (Coefficient · 1.85366e-06)

The purposes of this structure determination were to confirm the proposed structure and to analyze the possible symmetry of the molecule. Potentially, the molecule could belong to group C_{2v} with two minor planes and a 2-fold

rotation axis. The molecule could also have lesser symmetry corresponding to point groups C_s or C_2 .

The structure of **2** was solved using the suite of programs in teXsan⁶. The F^2 file, corrected for Lorenz-polarization effects and produced by Denzo-SMN and Scalepack⁷ Collect program, was read into teXsan. The structure was solved and refined anisotropically for non-hydrogen atoms using full-matrix least-squares to an R 5.7% ($R_w = 5.6\%$) with a GOF of 3.33. The largest residual peak in the difference Fourier was 0.30 e/Å³.

An ORTEP diagram of a single molecule is shown in Fig. 1. The structure has no internal symmetry. The two phenyl rings of the benzyl groups are twisted almost at right angles to each other. The two $-CH_2COOEt$ groups do have very approximate local C_2 symmetry; one $-CH_2COOEt$ group extends up from its benzene ring and the other extends in the opposite direction. There are no unusual bond lengths, bond angles or intra-molecular contacts in the structure. The bond distances and the bond angles are given in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively.

Fig. 1. ORTEP drawing of **2**.

Experimental

M.ps. are corrected and were taken on a Thomas-Kofler hot-stage equipped with a microscope and a polarizer. IR spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 1420 spectrophotometer in nujol between polished NaCl plates, ¹H NMR spectra on Varian T-60 and Varian EM-390 spectrometers, ¹³C NMR spectra were determined on a JEOL FX-60 spectrometer (15.03 MHz in the Fourier transform mode) in con-

Table 2. Bond distances (Å) and their esds in 2

Atom	Atom	Distance	Atom	Atom	Distance
O(12')	C(1)	1.394(2)	O(12')	C(1')	1.450(3)
O(12')	C(1'')	1.430(3)	O(12'')	C(4)	1.394(3)
O(13')	C(9')	1.336(3)	O(13')	C(10')	1.457(3)
O(13'')	C(9'')	1.316(3)	O(13'')	C(10'')	1.463(4)
O(14'')	C(9'')	1.188(3)	O(14')	C(9')	1.197(3)
C(1)	C(2)	1.361(3)	C(1)	C(9)	1.420(3)
C(1'')	C(2'')	1.494(3)	C(1')	C(2')	1.491(3)
C(2')	C(3')	1.374(4)	C(2')	C(7')	1.379(3)
C(2)	C(3)	1.424(3)	C(2)	C(8')	1.511(3)
C(2'')	C(3'')	1.379(4)	C(2'')	C(7'')	1.364(4)
C(3'')	C(4'')	1.376(4)	C(3)	C(4)	1.377(3)
C(3)	C(8'')	1.510(3)	C(3')	C(4')	1.406(4)
C(4'')	C(5'')	1.349(5)	C(4)	C(10)	1.413(3)
C(4')	C(5')	1.376(4)	C(5)	C(6)	1.353(4)
C(5)	C(10)	1.420(3)	C(5'')	C(6'')	1.359(4)
C(5')	C(6')	1.349(4)	C(6'')	C(7'')	1.397(4)
C(6)	C(7)	1.392(4)	C(6')	C(7')	1.359(4)
C(7)	C(8)	1.369(3)	C(8)	C(9)	1.415(3)
C(8')	C(9')	1.498(4)	C(8'')	C(9'')	1.507(4)
C(9)	C(10)	1.406(3)	C(10')	C(11'')	1.364(5)
C(10')	C(11')	1.470(4)			
C(1'')	H(19)	0.96	C(1'')	H(20)	0.97
C(1')	H(21)	0.97	C(1')	H(22)	0.97
C(3'')	H(9)	0.98	C(3')	H(7)	0.97
C(4'')	H(14)	0.96	C(4')	H(11)	0.98
C(5)	H(3)	0.98	C(5'')	H(8)	0.97
C(5')	H(12)	0.97	C(6'')	H(6)	0.99
C(6)	H(5)	0.97	C(6')	H(13)	0.97
C(7'')	H(1)	0.97	C(7)	H(4)	0.98
C(7')	H(10)	0.98	C(8)	H(2)	0.97
C(8')	H(15)	0.97	C(8')	H(16)	0.97
C(8'')	H(17)	0.97	C(8'')	H(18)	0.96
C(10'')	H(25)	0.98	C(10'')	H(26)	0.98
C(10')	H(23)	0.97	C(10')	H(24)	0.97
C(11'')	H(30)	0.97	C(11'')	H(31)	0.94
C(11')	H(32)	0.95	C(11')	H(27)	0.94
C(11')	H(28)	1.02	C(11')	H(29)	0.93

junction with a TI-980B computer, chemical shifts in ppm downfield from TMS and low resolution MS on a Finnegan Quadrupole 4023 chromatograph-mass spectro-meter by a direct probe at an ionizing voltage of 70 eV. Microanalyses were performed by Atlantic Microlab, Inc. All reactions were monitored by tlc.

1,4,1a,4a-Tetrahydroanthraquinone (4) : It was pre-

pared in 72% yield by the published procedure⁴, m.p. 101–102° (lit.⁴ 102–103°); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.3–7.7 (4H, m, H-5, H-6, H-7, H-8), 5.7 (2H, m, H-2, H-3), 3.5 (2H, m, H-1a, H-4a), 2.4 (4H, m, H-1, H-4); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 197.8 (s, C-9, C-10), 134.4 (s, C-5a, C-8a), 134.2 (d, C-5, C-8), 126.8 (d, C-6, C-7), 124.6 (d, C-2, C-3), 46.6 (d, C-1a, C-4a), 24.4 (t, C-1, C-4); ν_{max} 1690, 1590 cm⁻¹; m/z 212, 194, 165, 105, 77.

Table 3. Bond angles and their esds in (2)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle
C(1)	O(12')	C(1')	114.9(2)	C(1'')	O(12'')	C(4)	114.7(2)
C(9')	O(13')	C(10')	116.0(2)	C(9'')	O(13'')	C(10'')	117.2(3)
C(12')	C(1)	C(2)	119.1(2)	O(12')	C(1)	C(9)	118.3(2)
C(2)	C(1)	C(9)	122.6(2)	O(12'')	C(1'')	C(2'')	109.8(2)
O(12')	C(1')	C(2')	120.2(3)	C(3')	C(2')	C(7')	121.7(3)
C(1')	C(2)	C(3)	119.4(2)	C(1)	C(2)	C(8')	118.9(2)
C(1)	C(2)	C(3)	119.4(2)	C(1)	C(2)	C(8')	118.9(2)
C(3)	C(2)	C(8')	121.5(2)	C(1'')	C(2'')	C(3'')	118.3(3)
C(1'')	C(2'')	C(7'')	122.9(3)	C(3'')	C(2'')	C(7'')	118.8(2)
C(2'')	C(3'')	C(4'')	120.1(3)	C(2)	C(3)	C(4)	118.8(2)
C(2)	C(3)	C(8'')	121.6(2)	C(4)	C(3)	C(8'')	119.6(2)
C(2')	C(3')	C(4')	120.3(3)	C(3'')	C(4'')	C(5'')	121.2(3)
O(12'')	C(4)	C(3)	119.3(2)	O(12'')	C(4)	C(10)	118.2(2)
C(3)	C(4)	C(10)	122.3(2)	C(3')	C(4')	C(5')	118.6(3)
C(6)	C(5)	C(10)	120.9(2)	C(4'')	C(5'')	C(6'')	119.5(3)
C(4')	C(5')	C(6')	121.4(3)	C(5'')	C(6'')	C(7'')	120.2(3)
C(5)	C(6)	C(7)	120.5(3)	C(5')	C(6')	C(7')	119.3(3)
C(2'')	C(7'')	C(6'')	120.2(3)	C(6)	C(7)	C(8)	120.6(3)
C(2')	C(7')	C(6')	122.4(3)	C(7)	C(8)	C(9)	120.3(2)
C(2)	C(8')	C(9')	111.9(2)	C(3)	C(8'')	C(9'')	112.4(2)
O(13')	C(9')	O(14')	123.9(2)	O(13')	C(9')	C(8')	110.7(2)
O(14')	C(9')	C(8')	125.4(2)	O(13'')	C(9'')	O(14'')	123.6(3)
O(13'')	C(9'')	C(8'')	111.4(3)	O(14'')	C(9'')	C(8'')	125.0(3)
C(1)	C(9)	C(8)	122.8(2)	C(1)	C(9)	C(10)	118.2(2)
C(8)	C(9)	C(10)	119.0(2)	O(13'')	C(10'')	C(11'')	110.7(3)
C(4)	C(10)	C(5)	122.6(2)	C(4)	C(10)	C(9)	118.7(2)
C(5)	C(10)	C(9)	118.7(2)	O(13')	C(10')	C(11')	107.4(3)

9,10-Dibenzoyloxy-1,4-dihydroanthracene (5): To a suspension of NaH (1.0 g, 40 mmol) in DMSO (4 ml) was added in an atm. of N₂ under stirring, a solution of **4** (2.0 g, 9.4 mmol) in DMSO (16 ml). After 30 min, the mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and freshly distilled benzyl chloride (4.4 ml, 38 mmol) was added. It was stirred for 3 h under N₂ at RT. After the usual work-up, the yellow solid was crystallized from C₆H₆-MeOH to give **5** (2.8 g, 75%) as colourless crystals, m.p. 144–146° (Found: C, 85.59; H, 6.21. C₂₈H₂₄O₂ calcd. for: C, 85.71; H, 6.12%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.5–8.2 (14H, m, ArH), 6.0 (2H, m, H-2, H-3), 5.1 (4H, s, Ar-OCH₂-Ph), 3.6 (4H, d, H-1, H-4); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 148.1 (s), 137.8 (s), 128.6, 128.5, 128.1, 127.7, 127.5 (s), 124.2, 122.3, 75.4, 24.8; *m/z* 392, 301, 209, 91.1.

9,10-Dibenzoyloxy-1,4-dihydroanthracene-2,3-oxide (6): To a solution of the dibenzyl ether (**5**; 5.0 g, 12.8 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (200 ml) was added *m*-CPBA (2.6 g, 15 mmol).

After stirring the mixture for 6 h at RT, aq. Na₂SO₃ (20%, 50 ml) was added. The organic layer was washed with 10% NaHCO₃ and brine, dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄, and evaporated to dryness. The yellowish residue (4.32 g) on crystallization from C₆H₆-hexane afforded **6** (3.6 g, 69%) as colourless needles, m.p. 164–166° (Found: C, 82.26; H, 5.94. C₂₈H₂₄O₃ calcd. for: C, 82.35; H, 5.88%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.3–8.0 (14H, m, ArH), 5.10 (4H, s, Ar-OCH₂-Ph), 2.8–3.8 (6H, m, H-1, H-2, H-3, H-4); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 148.9 (s), 137.5 (s), 128.6, 128.1, 127.7 (s), 127.5, 125.7, 122.7 (s), 122.2, 75.6, 51.1, 24.2; *m/z* 408, 317, 287, 91.

9,10-Dibenzoyloxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-trans-2,3-dihydroxyanthracene (7): A mixture of the epoxide (**6**; 2.69 g, 9.0 mmol), H₂O (50 ml) and H₂SO₄ (2.0 ml) was stirred overnight at RT. The resulting clear solution was neutralized with 2*N* NaOH and extracted with CHCl₃ (5 × 100 ml). After drying over Na₂SO₄, the organic layer was evaporated

to dryness, the residue (2.99 g) chromatographed on SiO₂ and crystallized from C₆H₆-hexane to yield **7** (2.69 g; 70%), m.p. 189–191° (Found : C, 78.78; H, 6.18. C₂₈H₂₆O₄ calcd. for : C, 78.86; H, 6.10%); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 7.4–8.0 (14H, m, ArH), 4.90 (4H, s, Ar-OCH₂-Ph), 3.90 (2H, m, Ar-CH-OH), 2.9–3.2 (6H, m, Ar-CH₂-CH(OH)-CH₂-CH(OH)-Ar); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 147.8 (s), 137.4 (s), 128.5, 128.0, 127.9, 126.8 (s), 126 (s), 125.5, 121.6, 74.7, 68.9, 29.9.

1,4-Dibenzyloxy-2,3-naphthalenediacetaldehyde (8) : To a solution of the diol (**7**; 21.0 g, 49 mmol) in MeOH (4.0 l) were added NaIO₄ (20.0 g, 93 mmol) and water (1.0 l). The mixture was stirred overnight in a water-bath at 45°. Water (100 ml) was added to it and the clear solution concentrated *in vacuo* to remove the MeOH. The precipitated salt was removed and the aqueous layer extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (5×100 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure to give a colorless oil (19.0 g, 90%). Three crystallizations from EtOH yielded pale yellow crystals (**8**; 1.0 g), m.p. 113–116° (Found : C, 78.95; H, 5.77. C₂₈H₂₄O₄ calcd. for : C, 79.25; H, 5.66%); ν_{\max} 2740, 1725 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 9.65 (2H, t, -CH₂CHO), 7.3–8.1 (14H, s, ArH), 4.8 (4H, s, -OCH₂-Ph), 3.6 (4H, d, -CH₂CHO); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 198.8, 150.3 (s), 136.8 (s), 128.6, 128.3 (s), 127.7, 127.6, 126.6, 122.7, 122.3 (s), 76.3, 42.8.

1,4-Dibenzyloxy-2,3-naphthalenediacetic acid (9) : To a solution of the dialdehyde (**8**; 1.1 g, 2.6 mmol) in Me₂CO (100 ml) at 5°, Kiliani reagent⁸ (20 ml) was added slowly under stirring. After stirring for 1 h at RT, a white precipitate separated. To the mixture, MeOH (5 ml) was added, stirred for 30 min and the solvent removed *in vacuo* to give a residue (0.95 g). Crystallization from MeOH-hexane afforded **9** (0.9 g, 76%), m.p. 220–222° (Found : C, 72.92; H, 5.23. C₂₈H₂₄O₆ calcd. for : C, 73.68; H, 5.78%); ¹H

NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 7.3–8.1 (14H, m, ArH), 4.9 (4H, s, -OCH₂-Ph), 3.7 (4H, s, Ar-CH₂COOH); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 172.5 (s), 149.4 (s), 137.1 (s), 128.6, 128.3 (s), 128.1, 127.6, 126.6, 125.3, 124.4 (s), 76.1, 32.9.

Ethyl-(1,4-dibenzyloxy-2,3-naphthalene)-diacetate (2) : A solution of the diacid (**9**; 0.3 g, 0.7 mmol) in absolute EtOH (20 ml) and conc. H₂SO₄ (3 drops) was refluxed overnight. The EtOH was evaporated *in vacuo*, aq. NaHCO₃ added to neutralize and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3×30 ml). The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the solvent *in vacuo* and crystallization from hexane gave **10** (0.23 g, 68%) as large colourless cubes, m.p. 81–82°; ν_{\max} 1740, 1400 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.3–8.2, (14H, m, ArH), 5.1 (4H, s, -OCH₂, Ph), 4.15 (4H, q, -COO-CH₂CH₃), 3.95 (4H, s, Ar-CH₂COO-), 1.2 (6H, t, -CH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 171.5 (s), 150.2 (s), 137.5 (s), 128.4 (s), 128.1, 127.7, 126.3, 124.4 (s), 122.8, 76.4, 60.9, 32.2, 14.1.

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